

MODERN APPROACH TO THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Annotation. This article will talk about innovations in the preschool education system that is developing in our country, the huge reforms being carried out, the development of new emerging preschool educational organizations, Family non-governmental and private kindergartens, measures to further increase the coverage of the child in the preschool education system.

Keywords: education, upbringing, development, development, innovation, inclusion, institution, educator.

Today, in our country, huge reforms are being carried out in all branches of the educational system. Particular attention is paid to the field of preschool education, which plays an important role in the future and prosperity of our country. After all, this system is the primary and most important link in society. At preschool age in children, mental activity increases, moral and physical qualities are formed. Therefore, a lot of work is being done on the development of the preschool sphere, both organizational and content.

As a result of the decisions and decrees adopted by the head of state on the sphere, new modern kindergartens were also built in remote villages, and in a short time the number of preschool educational organizations increased from 5,200 to 18,300. The pre-school coverage of children increased 2-fold to 60%. Due to the introduction of a public-private partnership mechanism in the industry, 7,400 private kindergartens with more than 223,000 seats were established. For these purposes, 1 trillion 850 billion in preferential loan funds were directed, creating about 20,000 new jobs. As a result of the opportunities and benefits provided by the state, private and family kindergartens also increased. Today, 1,700,000 children are raised in all preschools.

On may 24, 2021, at the meetings of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the discussion of issues of expanding the coverage of preschool institutions in the regions, measures were established to establish 2,000 family kindergartens with 34,000 beds in 53 districts. By allowing such nurseries to hire additional workers, a proposal to double the number of children to be accepted was approved.

The head of state emphasized that the main thing is the content of education and education, and set the task of free delivery of educational manuals and methodological materials to family kindergartens. For this, a total of 30 billion will be allocated by the state. Also, to provide such institutions with the necessary equipment, preferential loans of up to 30 million rubles are provided at a 5% rate.

Short-term courses on training and professional development of 12 thousand employees of preschool educational institutions were established.

In addition, the system of preschool education was expanded and ministries were created below:

The Ministerial system includes:

- Central apparatus of the ministry;
- territorial divisions;
- Institute for retraining and professional development of directors and specialists of preschool educational organizations • * editorial board of the Journal "first step";
- public preschool organizations;
- Innovation center of information and pedagogical technologies;
- Foundation for the development of preschool education;
- Specialized project-Research Institute;
- Infrastructure development engineering company;
- Pedagogical colleges of the Ministry of preschool education

Another source of expansion of preschool coverage in remote areas is public – private partnership-based kindergartens. Today, 50 percent of expenses for one child are subsidized in such institutions. The meeting was instructed to increase the amount of this subsidy to 75%, to cover 50% of the electricity and natural gas payment of private kindergartens from the state budget.

Construction of new kindergartens is also being continued by the state. In 2021-2022, there are plans to build 50 preschools in remote and remote areas of 23 districts. For this, 50 neighborhoods were selected with the lowest coverage rate and the number of children exceeding 250. The president gave instructions to build these kindergartens on the basis of advanced foreign experience, provide them with modern equipment and manuals.

References:

1. Рузиматов, Р. Я., Махкамов, Г. М., Отажонова, С. Р., & Турсунова, Ш. А. (2017). Промышленное развитие в Коканде, причины экологических проблем (1956-1975гг.). Высшая школа, (6), 77-78.

2. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal.
3. Isabayeva, M. M., & Otajonova, S. R. (2021). Pedagogical factors of preparation of future teachers of biology for professional-pedagogical activities. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(6), 48-51.
4. Otajonova, S. (2021, July). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND. In Конференции.
5. Otajonova, S. (2021). PESTS OF FRUIT ORCHARDS IN THE TERRITORY OF KOKAND: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1318>. In RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES (No. 18.06).
6. Асқарова, М. А., Отажонова, С. Р., Алимова, М. Б., & Ирматова, М. Д. (2020). READING-INTELLIGENCE AS A CAPACITY-BUILDING TOOL. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(7), 398-402.
7. Rakhimova, G., Narimonova, Z., Otajonova, S., & Abdulxaeva, M. (2019). Stereotypy and poetics of the endemic of recit. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 11(7), 966-969.
8. Norquzieva, D. S., & Abdullaeva, N. R. (2019). PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENCE. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(6), 490-495.
9. Khamidovna, M. I., Sheralievna, N. D., & Okhunovna, M. D. (2022). CONFLICT MANAGEMENT AND TYPES OF CONFLICTS AMONG MINORS. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(7).
10. Sheralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 1212-1216.
11. Sheralievna, N. D. (2021). DYNAMICS OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR FORMATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(10), 666-669.
12. Sheralievna, N. D. (2022). FORMATION OF CONSTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR AS A FACTOR IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EDUCATION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 1212-1216.
13. Norqo'Ziyeva, D. S. (2021). ILK O'SPIRINLARNI KASBGA YO'NALTIRISHNING AYRIM PSIXOLOGIK MASALALARI. *Scientific progress*, 1(6), 1188-1192.
14. Бойтемирова, З., & Орипов, Э. (2016). РОЛЬ ДЕМОКРАТИЧЕСКИХ ИНСТИТУТОВ В ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ НАСЛЕДОВАНИЯ ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ

ЦЕННОСТЕЙ. In СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ В СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ СИСТЕМАХ (pp. 30-32).

15. Boytemirova, Z. (2020). Youth and Spiritual Security. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 181-183.

16. Aminova, M. M. (2021). The value of “5 initiatives” in the spiritual and moral education of students of secondary school. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(6), 38-42.

17. Mutalibovna, A. M. The Impact of Globalization on National Culture and Its Protection Problems. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 210-212.

18. Mutalibovna, A. M. The Modern Importance of Studying the Scientific Heritage of Ibn Khaldun. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 229-232.

19. Аминова, М. М. (2020). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ВОСПИТАНИИ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ МОЛОДЕЖИ. *Интернаука*, (22-2), 51-52.

20. Mutalibovna, A. M. INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO MODERN YOUTH EDUCATION.

21. Shamsiddinov, B. J., & Jakbaraliyva, Z. (2022). Scientific and Empirical Relations of Philosophy and Literature. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 7, 70-73.

22. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж., & Жакбаралиева, З. О. (2022). АБУ АЛИ ИБН СИНО ТИББИЙ ТАРБИЯ ХУСУСИДА. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 3(2), 670-674.

23. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж., & Алиев, А. А. Ў. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА КЎППАРТИЯВИЙЛИК ТИЗИМИ ВА ХУСУСИЙ ТАДБИРКОРЛИК. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 3(2), 675-682.

24. Jakbrovich, S. B. (2021, July). THE RELATIONS OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP WITH SELF-GOVERNMENT INSTITUTIONS. In *Euro-Asia Conferences* (pp. 64-69).

25. Jakbarovich, S. B. (2021, July). DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A SOCIO-ECONOMIC BASIS OF CIVIL SOCIETY. In *Euro-Asia Conferences* (pp. 69-72).

26. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ МАЪНАВИЙ ҲАЁТИДА ТАДБИРКОР ВА ИШБИЛАРМОНЛАР ИШТИРОКИНИНГ ЎРНИ ВА УНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ ТАЛҚИНИ. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 2(4), 565-574.

27. Шамсиддинов, Б. Ж. (2021). ХУСУСИЙ ТАДБИРКОР ВА ИШБИЛАРМОНЛАР ФАОЛИЯТИНИНГ ОИЛА ВА МАҲАЛЛА ФАРОВОНЛИГИГА ТАЪСИРИ. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 2(4), 452-456.
28. Бойкузиева, Г. (2020). ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ЖЕНЩИН В СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ ЖИЗНИ ОБЩЕСТВА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 27-31).
29. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2017). Тарих фалсафий тадқиқот предмети сифатида. *Молодой ученый*, (4-2), 26-27.
30. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2017). Бағрикенглик ижтимоий-фалсафий қадрият. *Молодой ученый*, (4-2), 27-28.
31. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2016). Теоретическая подготовка студентов к социологическим исследованиям в практической и самостоятельной работе. In *Молодежь и наука: реальность и будущее* (pp. 318-319).
32. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2016). Некоторые аспекты проблемных концепций осмысления динамики научного знания. In *Молодежь и наука: реальность и будущее* (pp. 245-247).
33. МИРАХМЕДОВ, Ж. М., & БАБАЕВА, Н. М. (2016). К ВОПРОСУ О СУЩНОСТИ СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ. In *Будущее науки-2016* (pp. 16-19).
34. Muhsinovich, M. J. (2020). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPTS OF SPIRITUAL SAFETY AND HISTORICAL CONSCIOUSNESS. *European science review*, (9-10), 39-41.
35. Mirakhmedov, J. M. (2020). SOCIAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPTS OF NATIONAL AND SPIRITUAL SECURITY. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(8), 171-174.
36. Muhsinovich, M. J. (2020). FEATURES OF MANIFESTATION OF HISTORICAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN NATIONAL-SPIRITUAL SECURITY. *Евразийский Союз Ученых*, (4-9 (73)), 65-66.
37. Мирахмедов, Д. М. ФИЛОСОФСКИЙ ПОДХОД ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО РАЗУМА.
38. Aminjonovna, S. O. (2021). The Importance of The Spiritual Heritage of Uzbek Enlighteners in the Education of Youth.
39. Орипов, Э. Ш., & Худойбергганов, Ш. Ш. (2020). ВИРТУАЛЬНЫЙ МИР: СОДЕРЖАНИЕ И СУЩНОСТЬ. In *ВОПРОСЫ НАУКИ 2020: ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НАУКИ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ* (pp. 53-60).

40. Худойбергганов, Ш. Ш., & Орипов, Э. Ш. (2020). ШОТЛАНД ОЛИМИ УИЛЬЯМ ЭРСКИН НИГОҲИДА БОБУР ТИМСОЛИ. In ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ (pp. 187-190).
41. Oriпов, E. S. (2021). HISTORICAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL ROOTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TRADITIONAL VALUES. Journal of Central Asian Social Studies, 2(01), 122-127.
42. Орипов, Э. Ш., & Абдурахмонов, З. М. (2020). ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ НОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ. In ВОПРОСЫ НАУКИ 2020: ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НАУКИ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ (pp. 61-68).
43. Shavkatovich, O. E. (2022). MILLIY G'OYA VA AN'ANAVIY QADRIYATLARGA DIALEKTIV YONDOSHUV. Oriental Art and Culture, 3(1), 261-265.
44. Abdurahmonovich, A. H. (2021). THE ISSUE OF INTERPRETING THE WORLD (BEING) NATURE ON THE THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF NATIONAL EDUCATION OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 2(07), 140-143.
45. Abdurahmonovich, A. H. (2022). A METHODOICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACH TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING 7TH GRADE EDUCATION IN A GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(12), 187-188.
46. Ортиқов, О. И. (2020). ИЖТИМОЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ МЕРОСДА МИЛЛИЙЛИК МАСАЛАСИ. Интернаука, (10-3), 63-65.
47. Urinboyev, D. (2019). Thoughts About Stratagema Of Western And Eastern Thinkers. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 1(4), 147-151.
48. Bakhtiyorovich, U. D. (2022). Features of the manifestation of strategems and the relationship between them. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 96-100

